

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONTENT AND METHODS OF TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS TO EFFECTIVELY ORGANIZE EDUCATIONAL LESSONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the social competence of a teacher of the subject "Education" is a form of social work, which is manifested in pedagogical work with the population, colleagues, students and their parents. We note that the difference between a professional teacher of the subject "Education" and a citizen, a person who intuitively, and sometimes impulsively, guides, exerts an educational influence based on personal experience and professional requirements, is primarily manifested in the connection with a clear understanding of the goal, predicting results, theoretical, methodological and technological preparation, constant purposeful work, and work on oneself. The need and essence of the content of the modernization of educational work and social competencies of teachers in our country were substantiated in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2019 No. 1059 "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation". According to the Resolution The work being carried out in Uzbekistan on the modern basis of scientific and technological reform of youth education requires the formation of scientifically based basic competencies and qualities, based on the needs of today. The task of the teacher of education is to ensure the participation of cognitive and operational components of social competence. This is based on the state educational standard and curricula of general secondary education, it is necessary to form in students, as age-appropriate basic spiritual and moral virtues (competencies), such as loyalty to the Motherland, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, and hard work. At the same time, in order to restore and further enhance our great spirituality in our country under the conditions of independence, improve the national education system, and harmonize it with the requirements of the times, the issues of bringing the work of training qualified personnel to the level of world standards were considered.*

Keywords: *education, principle of adaptability, pedagogical system, students' educational, physically healthy, component, concept.*

INTRODUCTION

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that “ we have no right to forget what a unique wealth intellectual and cultural potential is, and that it is crucial to educate and bring to perfection those with rare talents.” Education is not just about teaching certain rules, but also about forming a person’s inner world, attitude to values, and raising him to be a person loyal to the Motherland and useful to the community.

Therefore, educators, especially specialists in primary education, must have a deep knowledge of the discipline of education and be able to effectively apply it in their activities. On August 23, 2019, the Ministry of Public Education, chaired by the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev , held a video conference dedicated to the development of the public education system, increasing the qualifications and authority of educators in society, and raising the spirituality of the younger generation. In order to ensure the implementation of the instructions given at the meeting of the Electoral College, a draft resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On measures for the gradual introduction of the subject “Education” in general secondary educational institutions” was developed. On July 6, 2020, Resolution No. 422 “On measures for the gradual introduction of the subject “Education” in general secondary educational institutions” was adopted. In accordance with the resolution, the subject “Education” will be introduced in general secondary educational institutions in grades 1–9 from the 2020-2021 academic year, and in grades 10–11 from the 2021-2022 academic year, combining the subjects “Etiquette”, “Sense of the Homeland”, “The Idea of National Independence and Fundamentals of Spirituality” and “History of World Religions”. It will be gradually implemented within the total hours allocated to subjects starting from 2019. The resolution approved the concept of the subject “Education” for students of general secondary educational institutions. Based on the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PQ-4884, a comprehensive program of measures was developed to further improve the fields of education and science . This program sets the task of periodically republishing the “ Education” textbook for grades 1-9, using the works of our great grandfathers .

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In order for the educational process to "preserve" its uniqueness, "Upbringing, training .. The co-authors of the monograph V.A. Karakovsky, Novikova, Selivanova, and others use another concept proposed by the famous Estonian pedagogue and psychologist O. Yo. Laimce. If we look at the educational process " according to Laimce ", then the educational system does not consist of didactics, but, on the one hand, a psychological-pedagogical system, and on the other - a socio-pedagogical system. 23 This, in turn, affects students not only didactically (through teachers, lessons, textbooks, homework), but also as a social factor, through the involvement of children in the environment; it affects through the relationships that arise between parents, teachers, and children, through the psychological environment that is formed at the very beginning of each lesson.

The concept of "didactic system" has been formed quite strongly in pedagogy. The didactic system of the school is expressed through educational goals, content of study, methods and forms of its organization. Of course, educational goals are also implemented in the teaching process by determining the content of the material being studied, the form and methods of its delivery, etc. But in the logic of the second concept of education, the didactic system itself participates in the didactic system of the educational system, that is, it is its system.

Education is the process of forming the younger generation into useful, morally perfect, spiritually mature and physically healthy individuals for society. This process is an integral part of the activities of every educator , and the discipline of education is especially important in the training of future teachers. The main goal of teaching the discipline of education is to provide future educators with in-depth knowledge of the theory and practice of education, to prepare them as competent educators who can properly organize the educational process, use modern methods and be fully qualified educators.

The essence of this goal is reflected in the following:

- to form knowledge about the content, principles, and laws of the educational process in future teachers;

- to educate them as individuals who are committed to national and universal values and who approach educational activities responsibly;
- to develop skills in the correct application of educational methods and technologies in practice ;
- preparation for the formation of an individual approach in educational work with students.

Future educators will perform the following tasks while studying education:

1. Mastering the theoretical foundations of the educational process. Gaining in-depth knowledge of the goals, objectives, content, principles, methods and tools of education. Familiarity with various educational concepts.
2. Formation of pedagogical thinking. Development of independent thinking skills through analysis of educational situations, identification of the problem and search for ways to solve it.
3. Develop skills in designing and organizing educational work. Learn to create scenarios for educational activities, effectively organize educational work in the classroom and outside the classroom, and conduct activities that prepare students for social life.
4. Acquire knowledge and approaches in the areas of moral, spiritual, aesthetic, ecological and labor education. Prepare to conduct educational work in various areas of education based on modern approaches, national and universal values .
5. Development of pedagogical culture and professional qualities. Formation of professional ethics and aesthetics through familiarization with the teacher's speech, dress code, manners, and rules of conduct .
6. Development of independent creative approach and innovative thinking. Development of skills in applying new methods in educational activities, developing creative projects, and using modern technologies .

By mastering the science of education, a future teacher will be able to organize each lesson in an educational direction and create a positive atmosphere in the classroom.

Is an important component of the pedagogical education system and plays a decisive role in preparing future teachers for professional activity. Through this discipline, the teacher acquires not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills and a responsible attitude to educational activities. Therefore, every teacher should study the discipline of education in depth and be able to effectively apply it in his practical activities.

Lectures and theoretical concepts alone are not enough to effectively teach future teachers about education. In this regard, modern, innovative approaches are very effective, including:

- problem-based learning;
- interactive methods (discussion, role-playing games, brainstorming);
- training and group work technology;
- analysis based on real-life situations.

Such approaches not only serve to better master the content of the subject, but also to form in the student the skills to correctly apply the educational approach in real situations.

The factors for organizing primary education lessons based on an innovative approach are the following:

- creating certain conditions for organizing primary education classes based on an innovative approach;
- organizing special training seminars aimed at revealing the essence of interactive methods among teaching staff;
- to achieve their thorough mastery of the basics of pedagogical technology; • to foster in teachers a sense of creative approach to the organization of educational activities;
- to develop skills and competencies in teachers to organize lessons based on a technological approach;
- to ensure that teachers organize educational work based on interactive methods;
- improving teachers' skills in organizing pedagogical activities on a technological basis;
- ensuring the effectiveness of primary education lessons. There are a number of principles for developing the skills of teachers to organize pedagogical activities based on interactive methods.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In today's globalization environment, the education of our country's youth has risen to the level of state policy, and therefore one of our main tasks is to protect the youth, the creators of our future, from various foreign ideas, ideologies and aggressions aimed at capturing the hearts and minds of people. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "The education of the younger generation has always been important and relevant. However, in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is truly becoming a matter of life and death. In today's modern Uzbekistan, the field of spirituality, enlightenment, and education, like all other areas, needs innovations. In Europe, South Korea, Japan, China, and Russia, there are hundreds of organizations, foundations, and associations engaged in scientific strategies for youth education.

Studying their experience, bringing in modern technologies and using them for the purpose of educating young people in the spirit of the national idea is one of the important requirements of the modernization of higher education. After all, the effectiveness of all reforms being carried out, our Development Strategy depends on the human factor, its spirituality. Therefore, the issues of the national idea, ideological education and spirituality-enlightenment remain a priority direction of our state policy. While nations and countries that are indifferent and indifferent to ideological education will cause their name and identity to disappear from the face of the earth, the nation that educates young people in the spirit of the modern national idea will live forever. Therefore, in the current complex and dangerous period, when ideological, ideological, and informational struggles are intensifying in the international arena, it is important to organize spiritual and educational work based on the requirements of the times, to form a conscious attitude of our compatriots to life, to increase their sense of involvement in the events taking place around them, and to wage a consistent fight against aggression that could threaten the independence of our country and our peaceful life.

Experts who are taking an objective approach to the crisis processes taking place in various spheres of life in Western countries, particularly in cultural life, are sadly noting that the Western world is on the verge of collapse. No matter how much the spiritual values of other nations influence our society, our national spiritual qualities, such as respect for elders and parents, humility, honesty, faith, hard work, and hospitality, remain stable. Because these spiritual qualities are ingrained in our blood. "Popular culture" that contradicts our people's spiritual values of

morality, thought, shame, honesty and purity, and human dignity is having a negative impact on the spirituality of young people.

The future of our country, the prospects of the new Uzbekistan, the success of the reforms being carried out in the field of education largely depend on the scientific potential, level, dedication of pedagogical personnel, their desire to educate the younger generation and raise them to the level of a well-rounded person. The educational process in any educational institution is organized and carried out directly by teachers. The spiritual and educational activities carried out in our country are based, first of all, on the spiritual and educational heritage of our people. After all, this heritage is a strong source of national ideology, our spirituality. The ideological education of today's students and future specialists requires the implementation of a new task that has not been set before. That is, while previously students were limited to learning about the national idea, destructive and constructive ideas, now they are required to be taught how to apply this knowledge in life.

After all, ideological education, by its very nature, involves educating young students as socially active specialists. Modernized ideological education transforms ideological awareness and competencies into everyday life skills and behavioral norms of young people. Technological components of spiritual and educational work are methods and techniques aimed at forming the necessary socio-political, ideological and ideological, moral knowledge, skills, qualifications, competencies and strong ideological immunity, high spiritual and moral qualities in the population and young people, influencing their consciousness, psyche and activity.

The content of the technology of spiritual and educational work consists of the following areas, which are implemented in the family, in preschool education, general education schools, higher and secondary specialized educational institutions, military units, as well as in cooperation with self-government bodies, all state and public organizations:

- to comprehensively stimulate the interest of the youth of our country in various fields of art, the culture of fandom, to establish systematic activities to enhance the importance of cinema and theater among different strata of our people, and to ensure their popularity;

- instilling feelings and concepts related to the upbringing of a complete person in the hearts and minds of the younger generation through effective methods in the family, neighborhood, school, academic lyceum, higher education institutions, and non-educational institutions, and developing the heritage of our ancestors in this regard in line with the requirements of today's development;

- develop scientific and practical programs to effectively and systematically combat ideological attacks directed against the centuries-old spirituality, national and religious values of our people;

- creating a system of advanced training for those responsible for spiritual and educational work in educational institutions, state and non-state organizations, and enterprises, and increasing the effectiveness of teaching subjects related to the foundations of the national idea and spirituality;

- formation of a reserve of personnel for spiritual and educational work, organization of special training courses for reserve personnel;

- develop a mechanism to encourage the implementation of best practices and innovative ideas in order to increase the effectiveness and impact of spiritual and educational activities.

- organizing the creation of documentary and feature films on current topics, as well as educational films, aimed at children, adolescents, youth and adults, dedicated to the promotion of national spirituality and in an educational direction;

- increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational outreach work in working with young people, creating an effective mechanism in this regard based on the capabilities of modern information technologies;

- Establishing cooperation with relevant organizations to study the social environment and public sentiment, based on the spiritual needs of the population and youth regarding spiritual, moral, political, social, and religious issues.

and practice of the educational system in higher education institutions, analyzing the modern activities of the system, and comprehensively studying pedagogical and other scientific literature shows that didactics and educational theory are taken into account in organizing the activities of the system of professional education of students.

The main requirements for the system of professional education of students are reflected in the following principles:

- the principle of expediency - the organizational and structural construction of the system in accordance with certain concepts, main ideas, programs, tasks and goals;

- the principle of integrativity – requires the integration of separately differentiated parts and functions of the system into a single whole and gives integrity to this process;

- the principle of educational education - active use of the educational potential of students in the content of the subjects being taught in order to develop their personal development, form positive motivation for self-improvement, and direct them to creative and practical activities outside of school;

- the principle of uniformity of requirements for professors and teachers and group trainers - implies that the requirements of all objects of the educational process are mutually agreed upon;

- the principle of adaptability - is implemented by adapting the pedagogical system to external and internal factors and conditions;

- the principle of scientificity - a scientific approach - in substantiating the conceptual aspects of the functioning and development of educational systems;

- the principle of professional orientation - the assimilation of the moral and ethical rules of the professional community by future specialists;

- The principle of systematicity, continuity and continuity of the activities of the system of professional education of students requires the comprehensive fulfillment of all tasks and the prevention of imbalance and fragmentation.

The above considerations require solving a number of problems in the modernization of modern ideological education.

In particular: - creating a broad ideological information environment in public life ;

- to identify the need for young people to acquire knowledge about the national idea and to ensure that they thoroughly master this knowledge, acquire practical skills and qualifications;

- modernizing the pedagogical foundations of instilling the national idea in the minds of young people ;

7 - Increasing the scope and quality of spiritual and educational events organized in higher education institutions and ensuring their viability are among these. After all, ideological disputes and information attacks in the world are placing new, modern demands on the ideological education of the growing younger generation. The need to neutralize the influence of foreign ideologies in higher education institutions is being emphasized. Spiritual and educational work in higher educational institutions is effective only when it is based on certain principles. The main principles that determine the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work include: national

ideological orientation, non-partisanship, unity of education and upbringing, vitality, integrity, unity of consciousness and behavior, practicality, mass participation, encouragement of student initiative, encouragement of good qualities, combating spiritual vices with "Enlightenment against ignorance", taking into account the future professional characteristics of students, and coherence.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that the ideological education of today's students, future specialists, based on the requirements of the new era of Uzbekistan's development, requires modernization on a scientific pedagogical basis, within the framework of preparing students for independent professional spiritual life. That is, if previously it was limited to providing students with knowledge about the national idea, destructive and creative ideas, modernized ideological education transforms ideological awareness, competencies into the daily life skills of young people, norms of behavior. After all, at the current stage, the development from national revival to national advancement requires students not only to know the content of spiritual and moral qualities, but also to have the ability to apply them in their daily practical activities.

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